

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DUBE****FIRST NAME: NOMSA****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied X UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author X did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author X did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 16%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR ACADEMIC WRITING

1. Which of the following can be categorised as academic writing?

- Monograph
- Dissertation
- Conference paper
- All the above¹**

2. Which rule of style is most preferred by EUCLID?

- Turabian²**
- BBC

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 7.

² EUCLID, *Initial Student Orientation* (Bangui: Euclid University 2021), 2.

- Google
 - Grammarly
3. Under what circumstances is direct quotation acceptable?
- When you have to increase the length of your essay
 - When there is a problematic word or phrase you do not understand
 - To make sure you have enough items in the bibliography
 - When an authority figure says something that can help you persuade the reader³**
4. Which of the following best describes Applied Research?
- Research that addresses a conceptual problem that has practical consequences⁴**
 - Research that is based on the researcher's personal experiences
 - Research in which the researcher becomes part of the research
 - A study of technological applications
5. Which of the following constitutes plagiarism?
- You quote, paraphrase, or summarise a source but fail to cite it.⁵**

³ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 36.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth Edition. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 29.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 80.

- Absence of bibliography
 - You use the same research methodology used by another researcher
 - You quote the same sources as another researcher
6. Which reference management tool is recommended by EUCLID?
- Grammarly
 - Zotero⁶**
 - Turnitin
 - SPSS
7. Which research methodology is characterised by *an underlying assumption that rich data that is nested in a real context can be captured only by way of the interactive process between the researcher and the research participants?*
- Statistical methods
 - Quantitative research
 - Chi-Square
 - Qualitative research⁷**
8. Which of the following **is not** a qualitative research methodology?⁸

⁶ EUCLID, *Initial Student Orientation*, 7.

⁷ Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth Edition (Chicago: Sage Publications, 2019), 145.

⁸ Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 157-175.

Experimental research design

- Ethnography
- Phenomenology
- Case study

9. *A purposeful sampling procedure was used to select this study's sample. The researchers sought to locate individuals at a variety of universities. A snowball sampling strategy was employed, whereby participants were asked to refer other individuals whom they knew.* Under which topic in a dissertation would the statement above be most appropriately positioned?

 Research sample⁹

- Literature review
- Bibliography
- Description of findings

10. *The researcher is an M & E practitioner employed in the PSC. As such, he has access to evaluative data of the government, and the DSD. A possible conflict of interest exists when using data from the PSC. However, the information used in this study is from*

⁹ Ibid.,179.

*published reports, which are already in the public domain.*¹⁰ Which aspect, crucial for qualitative research, was the researcher addressing by this statement?¹¹

- Sampling frame
- Sample representativeness
- Ethical considerations**¹²
- Relevance of study

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

¹⁰ Indrakumaran Arumugam Naidoo, "The role of monitoring and evaluation in promoting good governance in South Africa: A case study of the Department of Social Development" (PhD diss, University of Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, 2011), 92.

¹² Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 46, 469.

EUCLID. *Initial Student Orientation*. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth Edition. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Bloomberg, Linda D. and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*. Fourth Edition. Chicago: Sage Publications, 2019.

Naido, Indrakumaran A. "The role of monitoring and evaluation in promoting good governance in South Africa: A case study of the Department of Social Development". PhD. Diss., University of Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, 2011.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.